

TRANSLATION ISSUES IN THE PRAGMATIC ASPECT

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Annotation. *The article studies the issues related to translation by the translator and the establishment of a pragmatic attitude of the receptor to the transmitted communication, which affects the creation of the image and content of the translation. The author points out the need to reproduce the pragmatic potential of the original and the desire to provide the desired effect on the translation receptor, which he calls the pragmatic aspect or pragmatic translation. The issues of the specifics of translation studies in a bilingual language situation in the process of oral and written communication are also discussed. Transfers are distributed according to different criteria: by the completeness of the transmitted content, by the target and thematic orientation. The author gives the categories of translation: technical, literary (artistic), economic, medical, legal.*

Key words: *translation, pragmatic attitude, receptor, pragmatic translation, content, technical, literary (artistic), economic, medical, legal.*

There is no secret that pragmatic aspect in translation is considered to be the most difficult issue to overcome and transfer since literal straightforward translation not only cannot render true sense of translation but also it can distort the meaning.

Thus, pragmatic aspect is mainly managed with Pragmatic adaptation of the content - bringing the content into a form that facilitates its perception as much as possible and contributes to the provision of an appropriate communicative effect. Pragmatics of translation is a wide notion which covers not only pragmatic meaning of a word, but some problems connected with various levels of understanding by speech acts communicants of certain meanings or messages, depending on linguistic

or paralinguistic factors, that is, background knowledge. A well-known linguist V.N. Komissarov points out that pragmatic aspect of translation should be considered from three points. One of them is conveying pragmatic meaning of words. This point chiefly pertains to the translation of national realia and equivalent lacking words that is, various names.

The term pragmatic meaning of a word is not yet fully investigated. But some linguists point out that the pragmatic component of the word meaning, which is realized in various kinds of emotive and stylistic connotations, is individually-occasional or collectively used meanings. They reflect the conditions of a language unit use, the conditions such as situation and place of communication, subject and purpose of communication; social, ethnic, and individual peculiarities of communicants, their attitude towards one another. Irrespective of the fact whether pragmatic aspects are singled out into a certain type of a word meaning or whether it is considered among other components of its meaning, pragmatic meaning, which is fixed in a word, plays an important role and its retention ensures complete communicative adequacy of translation to the original.

Pragmatics as a linguistic term means the analysis of language in terms of the situational content, within which utterances are made, including the knowledge and beliefs of the speaker and the relation between speaker and listener. Pragmatic information is actualized in translating the equivalent–lacking lexical units, first of all personal names, geographical names, national realia by way of transcription and transliteration.

The importance of adaptation is highlighted with the following statement by Vinay, Darbelnet: “If a translator systematically refuses to adapt, it will eventually lead to a weakening of a target content”. [6; 33] This point of view provides a clear understanding of adaptation as an unavoidable part of the translation process which aims at strengthening the connection between source and target contents and between source and target audiences, too.

Now that the notion of pragmatic adaptation is defined, we need to find out what source content criteria imply the use of pragmatic adaptation. Albrecht Neubert in his classification puts forward the following criteria:

“Stylistic aspects of a source content” (stylistic devices used in the source content, i.e. metaphors, epithets, personifications, similes, etc.)

“Expressive elements of a source content” which can be understood as various parameters of a source content register. Michael Halliday set the definition of the content register forth: ‘these are the linguistic features which are typically associated with a configuration of situational features of formality and informality – with particular values of the field (total event of communication), mode (the function of a content) and tenor (the type of interaction)’. [7, p 124]

Syntactic construction’ which provides special emphasis on a certain part of a source content (e.g., inversion). Extra contentual factors of a source content (time, functions, place of communication where a source content is produced) When pragmatic adaptation is applied to a particular part of a given content, a translator as one (or several) uses it of the following translation techniques of pragmatic adaptation:

- omission; (translator omits unnecessary information)
- expansion (explication of source information);
- exoticism’ (substitution by rough equivalents);
- updating (substitution by modern equivalents);
- creation (a target content preserves only the most essential information of a source content).

Andrew Chesterman and Emma Wagner consider pragmatic adaptation a strategy of translation and propose the following strategies of pragmatic adaptation “Explicitness change”.

This strategy helps to transform the information of a source content to make it more explicit or implicit. When the implicit information given in a source content is not sufficient for the target audience, a translator can make it explicit in a target content. A translator can, vice versa, omit some unnecessary information provided

in a source content, which would be an implicated, if the target audience is expected to deal with it.

Interpersonal change is a kind of strategy, applied, to give an example, when translating business letters, helps to change the level of formality, the degree of involvement and sense of a source content author.

Illocutionary change is strategy involves a change of moods (e.g., indicative to imperative), changes of the structure of rhetorical questions and exclamations, variation between direct and indirect speech.

Coherence change may include various types of the source content structure alterations (e.g., paragraphing). Partial translation is using when translator can reduce a source content to a summary.

Visibility change, when translators undertake changes in the level of the author's presence in the content. Alternatively, translators make themselves visible by adding footnotes, bracketed comments, etc.

Trans editing involves radical re-writing of a source content. To recap, pragmatic adaptation can be applied to some isolated parts of a source content which block target reader's proper understanding of this content. In this case, pragmatic 94 adaptation acts as one (or several) of enumerated translation techniques. If a source content, translated as is, represents a general difficulty for understanding, pragmatic adaptation can be opted for by a translator as a strategy applied to the source content as a whole.

We are talking about changing the content of the content, introducing additional information in the form of explanations, comments, or omitting information that is incomprehensible to the recipient of the translation, which is communicatively irrelevant, or replacing incomprehensible information with more understandable information, etc. Genre affiliation of the content largely affects the degree of its pragmatic adaptation. For example, scientific and technical style is characterized by fewer discrepancies in different languages, scientific and technical contents need less adaptation.

The method of pragmatic adaptation of the content include:

Explication of the information implied in the original through appropriate additions and explanations in the TL.

Additions and explanations are used when translating into Russian:

— in translating geographical names, it should be mentioned precise information
For example, Alberta is the Canadian province of Alberta.

— in translating the names of printed media, institutions the nominative point should be added

For example, *Newsweek is a Newsweek magazine.*

— if necessary, provide an understanding of the names of the realities associated with the peculiarities of the life and life of a foreign-speaking team.

— For example: “For dessert we got Brown Betty which nobody ate (Salinger)”
“They served red Betty for dessert, pudding with molasses, but no one ate it.”

— at the mention of the structures of state power.

For example (from Russian to English): when mentioning the State Duma in the English content, it is appropriate to make an explanation since by explanation audience to whom these terms are unknown could get into it:

State Duma, the lower house of the Russian Parliament. For the same purpose, page footnotes or notes to the whole content of the translation can be used.

The communicative orientation of the content usually corresponds to the type of utterance. For example, informing is provided through the use of declarative sentences, motivation - through the use of the incentive mood. However, there are exceptions to this rule that you should pay attention to at the stage of content analysis. For example, “I love apples” could mean “Give me an apple”. In normal situations, these statements have a different communicative orientation. But in some speech situations, the first statement may sound like a request. This should be taken into account when translating.

The main requirements for the result of the translation are:

— the content of the translation and the original must perform the same dominant function;

— the communicative effect produced by the translated content on its recipient should be approximately the same as the communicative effect produced by the original content.

Since each group of communicants belongs to a foreign language group, i.e. its own culture, therefore, has its own mentality, national psychology and worldview. The main pragmatic setting, according to Schweitzer, is to take into account differences in the perception of the same content by speakers of different cultures, participants in different communicative situations. Here differences in initial knowledge, representations, behavioral norms affect.

In the process of interlingual communication, the translator (who is not only bilingual, but also bicultural) has the opportunity to take into account the characteristics of potential recipients of the target content when creating the translation.

The task of ensuring adequate perception of the content by the recipient of the translation is most successfully solved when the translator has managed to reliably determine which particular group of readers (listeners) will act as the recipient of the translated content. In some situations, the translator knows this for sure. If he does not know this, then he tries to establish who the original content is intended for and tries to focus on the corresponding group of recipients of the translation.

Eugene Nida, speaking about the adequacy of the translation, notes that when the question arises which of the two translations of one content is better, the answer to this question should be sought in the answer to another question: “Better for whom?” [5]

It is obvious that car maintenance instructions are intended primarily for motorists and car service workers and should be clear to them. A scientific article on ways to improve soil fertility in central Russia, obviously, will be of interest only to specialists - agronomists.

The implementation of a pragmatic impact on the recipient of information is an essential part of any communication, including interlingual communication. Establishing the necessary pragmatic relation of the Translation Receptor to the

transmitted message largely depends on the choice of language means by the translator when creating the translation content. The influence on the dissertation and result of the translation process of the need to reproduce the pragmatic potential of the original and the desire to provide the desired impact on the translation receptor is called the pragmatic aspect or pragmatics of translation. The translator, acting at the first stage of the translation process as the Receptor of the original, tries to extract the information contained in it as fully as possible, for which he must have the same background knowledge that the “native speakers” of the source language have. The successful performance of the functions of an interpreter therefore presupposes a comprehensive acquaintance with the history, culture, literature, customs, modern life and other realities of the people who speak a foreign language. Like any Receptor of the original, the translator has his own personal attitude to the transmitted message. As a linguistic intermediary in interlingual communication, the translator should strive to ensure that this personal attitude does not affect the accuracy of reproduction in the translation of the original content. In this sense, the translator must be pragmatically neutral. 257. In the second step of the translation process, the translator seeks to ensure that the original message is understood by the Translation Receptor.

It takes into account that the Translation Receptor belongs to a different language community than the Original Receptor, has different knowledge and life experience, has a different history and culture. In cases where such discrepancies may prevent a full understanding of the original message, the translator eliminates these obstacles by making the necessary changes to the translated content. The absence of the necessary background knowledge of the Translation Receptor makes it necessary to explicate the implied information, to make appropriate additions and explanations to the content of the translation. This happens especially often in connection with the use of proper names, geographical names and names of various cultural and everyday realities in the original. When translating into Russian geographical names such as American Massachusetts, Oklahoma, Virginia, Canadian Alberta, Manitoba or English Middlesex, Surrey, etc., as a rule, the words

“state, province, county” are added indicating what these names mean, in order to make they are understandable to the Russian reader: the state of Massachusetts, the province of Alberta, the county of Middle Sex, etc. Adding explanatory elements may also be required when transferring the names of institutions, firms, publications.

There are contents that, albeit not immediately, find all of humanity as their addressee, for example, fiction. Here the translator has to focus on the so-called “average recipient of the content” Komissarov: “The best results were achieved by translators who were close in their views and creative manner to the author of the translated content.” However, he also notes that: “in modern conditions, a translator is required to be able to translate contents of various authors and trends in a qualified manner. He needs the ability to transform.” [7]

Translation studies is the science of translation as a process and as a content, which studies the problems of translation, the main stages of its formation and development, its theoretical foundations - general and particular, the methodology and technique of the translation process, the formation of translation skills and the ability to transfer information from one language to another in oral and writing. Thus, the main specificity of translation studies is the study of speech and language activity in a bilingual situation, when the process of communication (oral and / or written) is carried out by means of two languages.

A written translation includes many characteristics; therefore, its types are divided into categories. There is a distribution of translations in different criteria:

- on the completeness of the content transmitted,
- on the purpose of translation;
- on his thematic orientation.

Moreover, written translation includes the following categories:

- Technical. Features of the written translation of technical documentation provide for the exact interpretation of terms, units of measurement, technical abbreviations, designations in the drawings.
- Literary or so-called artistic translation. Such work should not only convey the meaning of the content, but also its character, genre, style. This is practically the

creation of a new literary work. Artistic translation includes the transfer of prose, poems, songs.

- Economic. The prerequisite is the presence of a profile knowledge or experience in this area. This is not only knowledge of the terminology of the original language, but also a constant study of the global economy.
- Medical. One of the most complex species. To translate a medical document, you need to perfectly own medical terminology, be able to use profile directories and dictionaries.
- Legal. The main problems of such work are a specific design and excellent ownership of the concepts of a legal system of different states.

Implementation of pragmatic impact on the recipient information is the most important part of any communication in including interlarded. Establishing required pragmatic translation receptor relationship to transmitted message largely depends on the choice translator of language means when creating the content of the translation. Impact on the dissertation and result of the translation process need to reproduce pragmatic potential Original and desire to ensure the desired impact on translation receptor is called pragmatic aspect or pragmatic translation.

When pragmatic adaptation is applied to a particular part of a given content, it's used by a translator as one (or several) of the following translation techniques of pragmatic adaptation: "omission" 'expansion' (explication of source information); 'exoticism' (substitution by rough equivalents); "updating" (substitution by modern equivalents); "creation" (a target content preserves only the most essential information of a source content). Andrew Chesterman and Emma Wagner consider pragmatic adaptation a strategy of translation and propose the following strategies of pragmatic adaptation "Explicitness change". [1, p.124-127] This strategy helps to transform the information of a source content to make it more explicit or implicit. When the implicit information given in a source content is not sufficient for the target audience, a translator can make it explicit in a target content. A translator can, vice versa, omit some unnecessary information provided in a source content, which would be an implication, if the target audience is expected to deal with it.

“Interpersonal change”. This kind of strategy, applied, to give an example, when translating business letters, helps to change the level of formality, the degree of involvement of an author.

Resources

1. Govorova V.F. The pragmatic function of a scientific text // Actual problems of pragmalinguistics in the context of intercultural communication: materials of the All - Russian Scientific Conference, 7 - 8 Dec. 2006. - Togliatti: TSU, 2006. pp. 124 - 127.
2. New in foreign linguistics. Issue 16: Linguistic pragmatics: collection of articles / edited by E.V. Paducheva. - M.: Progress, 1985.
3. Paducheva E.V. Semantic research (semantics of time and type in the Russian language; semantics of narrative). - Moscow: Yaz. rus. Kultury, 1996.
4. Rudnev V.P. Dictionary of Culture of the twentieth century: key concepts and texts. - Moscow: Agraf, 1997.
5. Syntax and semantics, v. 3 — Speech acts, N. Y. — S. F. — L., 1975.
6. Speech act theory and pragmatics, Dordrecht — Boston, 1980.
7. Stepanov Yu. S., In search of pragmatics, Izvestia of the USSR Academy of Sciences, ser. LiA, 1981, No. 4.